

Description

Economic - if the **researcher in SLR planning** calibrate **search strings** choosing the right keywords (**semantic filtering**) may **avoid irrelevant hits** that can be measured by **precision/recall ratio**, then the efforts to process this information will be reduced increasing **efficiency**.

